

FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT AND THE LEVEL OF AFFECTIVE DOMAIN OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The global disease outbreak of COVID-19 has resulted to different modalities of distance learning where assessing students' academic performance will not be monitored as it was when the learners are inside the classroom. This leads to the focus on assessment of the affective domain of students which is essential to improve academic achievement and the quality of the educational experiences provided. This study introduced the elements of formative assessment and assessed its effect to the level of affective domain of students. Descriptive correlational research design led in attaining the objectives of the study using a researcher made survey questionnaire on the perception on the elements of formative assessment and level of affective domain, participated by 150 grade 7 MDL students of San Pablo City Integrated High School of the academic year 2020-2021. Mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentages, ANOVA and Pearson product moment of correlation were the statistical treatments used. The findings showed that the elements of formative assessment in terms of classroom culture, learning goals, methodologies, incremental and interactive assessments, timely and specific feedback, and learning outcomes as perceived by the students is significantly related to their level of affective domain. This indicates that from low to high level of mathematics achievement, significant differences exist in the perception of the students on the elements of formative assessment and resulted to a moderate to strong correlation with the level affective domain. This implies that the elements of formative assessment have helped in the development of their affective domain. The study suggests to consider the elements formative assessment in planning the learning tasks to be given to students as part of the teaching and learning process to help in the development of their affective domain.

Keywords: Formative Assessment, Affective Domain, classroom culture, learning goal, methodologies, incremental and interactive assessments, feedback, learning outcomes